

SPECIFIC FEATURES OF THE ADDRESSING

¹**Odilov.B.B**

Scientific Supervisor,

²**Ziyadullayeva Mokhira Tagayevna**

2nd year master's student in the direction of Comparative linguistics,
linguistic translation studies (by languages) of Samarkand State
Institute of Foreign Languages.

<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7732410>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 03rd March 2023

Accepted: 13th March 2023

Online: 14th March 2023

KEY WORDS

*Addresse, communicative,
pragmatic, comparative.*

ABSTRACT

In this article, information is given about the specific features of addressing and the stages of development. This article, a communicative and pragmatic analysis of Uzbek and English addresses to individuals is carried out in order to identify their national and cultural specifics.

Teaching foreign languages in Uzbekistan has become very important since the first days of the Independence of our country which pays much attention to the increasing of education level of people, their intellectual growth. It is a natural phenomenon of the society which reflects eternal spirit of the people, its inner world, and national peculiarities of thinking, traditions and customs of people through thousands of years, shortly, the inner and outer essence of the people. The theoretical understanding of the communicative and pragmatic aspect of speech activity, which has recently taken one of the leading places in linguistics, can be carried out with a sufficient degree of efficiency when comparing the material of various languages, including typologically different ones. As V.N.Lartseva rightly believes, "The problems and methods of comparative typological analysis are relevant both for languages that are not genetically related to each other, and for languages belonging to the same genetic group" [14,203]. In the last few decades, a large number of studies on the comparative study of unrelated languages have appeared. Such Russian scientists as V.D. Arakin, J. Buranov, V.G. Gak, Gatiyatullina, G.A. Klimov, E.S. Kubryakova, Yu.B. Rozhdestvensky, A.G. Sadykova, R. A. Yusupov and many others made a significant contribution to comparative and typological linguistics, to the development of conceptual and methodological apparatus.

The comparative study of languages conducted in the direction of language -ethnos - culture, as well as culture - ethnos - language, allows us to identify linguistic, speech, communicative differences and similarities, features of national consciousness, reveals the structure of individual languages more deeply, and also makes it possible to determine guidelines for finding and justifying the causes of existing differences. "When teaching a foreign language, the effect is achieved if the distinctive features of a foreign language in comparison with the native one are taken into account in the learning process" [3, 97].

The address, as a specific contact-fixing agent, is one of the most commonly used speech units in English and Uzbek languages. The address is an integral part of speech etiquette and is used in a variety of communication situations, used by people with a variety of social characteristics, sent to different recipients. The study of the system of appeals is a specific tool

for analyzing the culture of native speakers, since the set of appeals used by representatives of various ethnocultures is a kind of reflection of the signs of communicants and situations of speech communication that are significant from the point of view of ethnopsychology and cultural tradition. Finally, both Uzbek and English addresses carry a significant communicative load not only by naming the addressee, but also by establishing and maintaining verbal contact with the interlocutor, while regulating the idea of the communication situation as a whole and about the speech positions of partners, their social and personal relationships.

In this article, a communicative and pragmatic analysis of Uzbek and English addresses to individuals is carried out in order to identify their national and cultural specifics. The research shows that appeals in their functional and semantic features bear the imprint of the culture of native speakers, which is associated with a wide range of communication situations in which various appeals are used, a significant communicative load of these units and a variety of forms.

Address phenomenon is important as well as frequent in social interactions. Appropriate address behavior is crucial for effective communication and successful maintenance of interpersonal relationships. Normally, address behavior is governed by politeness phenomenon, which is culturally bound. Misunderstanding and misinterpretation can lead to feelings of offence, insult, and suspicion on the individuals involved, which will result in break-down in cross-cultural communication. For instance, nonnative speakers of English often express their surprise at the wide use or distribution of reciprocal first naming among people in UK and USA.

This change from an address form employed to define intimate relationships within a family or among close friends or business associates to the one used to define general relationships between strangers, between people of asymmetrical age and occupational status, between students and professors, and between young people and their seniors, has been quite a recent development which has naturally stimulated cross-cultural studies of address behavior in different countries [2, 56].

Addressing takes place so frequently in social interactions that it is an important component of communicative competence. In principle, one cannot expect that the literal translation of the routine expressions of his own language into another will have the same effect in the target language. Nevertheless, in practice, the interference of one's mother tongue in using a foreign language seems to be inevitable for foreign language learner. An American scholar was greatly annoyed when addressed as Mr. or Mrs. instead of Professor by Russian speakers of English, who actually tried to show respect to him. A male Russian student in a university of the United States was also annoyed by the term "pet" directed to him from a cleaner. The student thought how that person could treat him as an animal, say, a dog or cat. He was quite unhappy until someone explained the good will of the cleaner towards her in using the term. There are more examples in actual interactions.

As a fact, a manorial lordship or ladyship is not connected to the [British honors system](#), but rather the [feudal](#) system [1,109]. Ownership of a [manorial](#) lordship will be noted on request in British passports through an official observation worded, "The Holder is the Lord of the Manor of [6, 33]. Females can inherit the feudal title of Lord of the Manor, unlike titles of

peerage. In addition, it is the only title that can be purchased. Lordships of the manor are considered non-physical property in England and are fully enforceable in the English court system. Like their English counterparts, by 1600 manorial titles in the formerly Norman territories in France and Italy did not ennoble their holders in the same way as, for example, did a barony. The status of lord of the manor is associated with the rank of esquire by prescription [5,203].

Based on studies by Rudkovskiy (1989) and Quirk (1985), there are six types of address forms: kinship terms, proper names, titles (occupational, official and social), pronouns, no-naming and others (terms of endearment and derogation, indefinite pronouns, nominal phrases and nominal clauses). Although the six categories of address forms exist in both languages, they vary greatly in contents and usage patterns. Besides, although social factors like age, kinship, acquaintances, generation, rank and setting and the principles governing politeness strategies are universal, the linguistic possibilities for the realization of politeness strategies are language specific, that is, different factor may carry different weight in the choice of address strategy in different languages. When comparing the two flow charts designed respectively by American linguist Ervin-Tripp [4,52] and Russian scientist B.Iyish [6,123], it is not difficult to find that in Russian address system, order of seniority and age play an important part in their choice of proper address forms especially when addressing relatives, neighbors and seniors. However, in American English address system, seniority and age exert influence mainly on people of higher generation (15 years older) in kinships, while first names instead of honorific titles can be used even when addressing older generations among friends and colleagues.

Let's now summarize the major differences in Uzbek, Russian and American English address use as follows: Recently, the trend of many English-speaking people has been to address others by using the first name than using titles like Mr. or Sir even when people meet for the first time. This applies not only to people of roughly the same age, but also of different ages. It is not a sign of disrespect. However, this is quite counter to Russian custom.

Kinship terms play an important part in the Uzbek and Russian language address systems. Age, generation and order of seniority are regarded as far more important than those in American system. The use of a person's title, office or occupation is quite common the Uzbek and Russian languages. Nevertheless, one seldom hears Uzbek Do'm bobo, Rais buva, Birgad. But English speakers addressing others as Bureau Director Smith, Manager Jackson, and Principal Morris. In English, only a few occupations or titles would be used which include Doctor, Judge, Governor, Mayor and Professor.

There are a lot of ways of address forms, rules, variations in the Uzbek and English languages. These rules are very similar to each other. How to address people appropriately needs the taking of several factors into consideration, such as the social status or rank of the other, sex, age, family relationship, occupational hierarchy, transactional status, race or degree of intimacy.

Despite of its occasional inefficiency, we will first look at the general rules of address forms. An English or American person can be addressed by his name, his title his name plus his name, or by nothing at all, that is, no-naming form.

Examples:

full name: *"A rise! Marry Johnson Black, you know we are at the party?"*

(2) first name: *"They are on your desk, Marry"*

(3) nickname: *"Joanna, there's something I have to tell you"*

(1) full name: Ibodovva Nargiza Aliyevna, bajarilgan ishlarning hisobotini topshiring. In Uzbek it means order or sarcasm.

(2) first name: *Aziza, bugun darslaringga bor. Qaytishda bozorga kirib kelarsan.*

(3) nickname: Hoy Qalamqosh, shuni ham tushunmadingmi?

2 Title Examples

(1) title concerning family relationship: *"All right now, children! Outside for your walk, mother's orders"*

(2) title of occupation: *"Operator, could you please put through a call to Copenhagen?"*

(3) title of rank: *"You are right, Mrs."*

(4) Honorifics: *"Your Royal Highness, twenty-four hours. They can't be blank]."*

(5) other titles: *"Oh, darling." / "You dogs!" / "What do you want, fellow?"*

(6) Title plus name: *Doctor Smith.*

(7) No-naming: *"Good morning"*.

2 Title Examples in Uzbek.

(1) title concerning family relationship: *"Aziz opa-singillarim, bu ishni bajarishimiz biz uchun farz. Axir u onamning vasiyatlariku!"*

(2) title of occupation: *Buyuring Xonim, sizga bo'lsin jon fido.*

(3) title of rank: *Boshliq, topshirig'ingiz bajarildi!*

(4) Honorifics: *Ko'zim nuri, qalbim qo'ri, Azizam! Sizni bahor ayyomida shunday latofatli holatda ko'rib turganimdan bag'oyatda baxtiyorman.*

(5) other titles:

Begonamas **mehribonlarim,**

Mehridaryo **onajonlarim,**

Yuzi issiq **jonajonlarim,**

Bayramingiz muborak bo'lsin!

(6) Title plus name: *So'z kengash raisi Jo'rayevaga beriladi.*

(7) No-naming: *Siz o'shami...?*

These address forms can be found in daily communication, both in oral and written forms. In addition to causing other people's attention, address forms have other important social functions, such as to show respect, to show intimacy, to honor or to humiliate other people.

There are differences even in the way different regions of the English-speaking countries use different forms of address. For example, the use of a person's first names in North America does not necessarily indicate friendship or power. First names are required among people who work closely together, even though they may not like each other at all. First names may even be used to refer to public figures, but scornfully as well as admiring.

The various use of address forms sometimes merely serves as a marker of regional difference, but sometimes it is enough to cause miscommunication.

T. Lechner reported that the address form "Mrs." has different meanings in the southern part of the United States than it has elsewhere. In the South, the term "Mrs." is often used a

substitution for the formula “I beg your pardon?” or “pardon?” in asking someone to repeat what he has said or to explain something. The contrast in the use of the two forms is exemplified in the following conversation [7,132].

(1) A: *Could you tell me how late you're open this evening?*

B: *Mrs.?*

A: *Could you tell me how late you're open this evening?*

B: *Until six.*

In addition, it was found that the phrase “Yes, Mrs.” is often used instead of “You're welcome” as a response to

“Thank you”. For example:

(2) A: *Could you tell me how late you're open this evening?.*

B: *Until five-thirty.*

A: *Thank you very much.*

B: *Yes, Ma'am.*

Not only is the form “Mrs.” gives different meanings in the South, it is also used in very different social contexts than elsewhere in the country. In the northeast, for example, “Mrs.” was found to occur between strangers and, to a lesser extent, from lower to upper status speakers. In the South, however, it was found that the term was used not only to strangers but also to acquaintance and even intimates. Thus, graduate students at the University of Virginia were heard to be addressed as “Mrs.” by their female professors were given this address form by their female colleagues, and wives were even heard to use this term to their own wives.

The form “daughter.” gives different meanings in the viloyats of our country. Sometimes it means address, sometimes honor.

Balam, shu chamandagul do'ppini topgunimcha rosa bozorni aylandim (Buxoro viloyati shevasida).

Ona qizim, bu dastorni sizning sepingizga qo'shish uchun olib keldim. (Vodiy shevasida).

While it is unlikely that women from other parts of the country would become offended if they were addressed as “Mrs.” in situations where they were unaccustomed to it. It is possible that southern women would misunderstand the absence of this form where they were used to expecting it, and would therefore regard non-southern speakers as rude or lacking in respect for men. But women have always been glorified in the Uzbek language.

One of the peculiarities of the Russian language today is the fact that there are no generally accepted neutral address words to appeal an unknown person – a man or a woman [8,67].

Such kinds of words were used before the Russian revolution (1917). They were сударь (sir) and сударыня (madam), господин (mister) and госпожа (mistress). The revolution changed not only life in Russia, but also the Russian language and speech. People started to frequently use the word “товарищ” (comrade) to address both men and women. In formal relationship, especially in the written speech and documents, the word гражданин (citizen) was used.

Along with disintegration of former Soviet Union the soviet word товарищ also vanished, but no new word took its stand. The empty space was filled by the expressions “Молодой человек!” (a young man) и “Девушка!” (a girl). Nowadays, if you want to address an

unknown person you can say “Молодой человек!” Please note that it’s absolutely unimportant how old the person you address to is – 20 or 60 years old or “Женщина” for old woman and “Девушка” for younger one. Don’t be confused to use these words and expressions and don’t think about their exact meaning [9,134].

In official situations, in the documents or when you see a person for the first time, it’s a tradition to use a name and a patronymic (father’s name in a special form): *Lyudmila Petrovna, Marina Nikolayevna*. However, young people because of their age and influence of Western culture prefer to give only their first names: *Alexei, Natalya, Anna* and *Sergey*. But an official “You” is preserved [12,21].

Among close friends, in the family and at school people don’t use their “full” names, they use diminutive forms. For example: for the name for *Maria* – *Masha*, for *Petr* – *Petja*, for *Leonid* – *Ljova*, etc.

There’s another short and tender form addressing people: *Sashenka, Serjozhenjka, Jenechka*. Kids and close ones can be called like this. This form is made with the help of different suffixes (-еньк, -оньк, ечк) to the short form of a name.

Thus, you can guess what relationships are between people if you know how people address each other.

The word «подруга» “a girlfriend” is an equivalent to the word “friend”, when a woman uses it. However, when a man, this word gets an additional “sexual” connotation use it. That’s why if a Russian man wants to say that he has only friendly relationship with a woman, he uses the word “an acquaintance”. But if he wants to show that there’s not only friendship, but love between them, he says: “my girlfriend”, “my girl”.

In Tsarist Russia, there used to be dozens of forms of address and were used only for mail ones. Some of them legislatively regulated. The official table of ranks listed 14 titles hierarchically, all to be addressed in different manners, from “*Your Excellency*” (*Ваше Превосходительство*) for the higher ranks to “*Your Nobleness*” (*Ваше Благородие*) for the lower ones. “*Your Honour*” (*Ваша Честь*), “*Your Grace*” (*Ваша Милость*), and “*Dear Sir*” (*Милостивый Государь*) were the accepted respectful form of address that could be used irrespective of the addressee's rank. The “*Dear Sir*” address could be abbreviated to “*Sir*” (*Сударь*), and there was also a variant for addressing females, “*Madam*” (*Сударыня*) [8,77].

So, as you can see, there is no universal word that we can all use. The safest bet is to use the person’s name or just a good old “*извините*” – “excuse me”.

The fact once again confirms that language is the mirror of social values. And the change that such a requirement is being discarded indicates the co-variation between social change and linguistic choice. In principle, one cannot expect that the literal translation of the routine expressions of his own language into another will have the same effect in the target language. But in practice, the interference of one’s mother tongue in using a foreign language seems to be inevitable for foreign language learner.

So, addressing as one of the most important means of attracting attention in the composition of statements of various communicative and pragmatic types is an important unit of speech etiquette. With the help of this communicative unit, speech contact with the interlocutor is established and maintained, the idea of the communication situation as a whole

and the speech positions of communication partners, their social and personal relationships are regulated. According to the rules of speech etiquette, the correct address should be present in every speech, only it is necessary to build it in accordance with the national rules of speech etiquette and the rules of its relevance in speech.

References:

1. Aitchison J. *Language Change: Progress of Decay?* – London: Cambridge University Press, 1999. – 172 p.
2. Bates E. & Benigni L. Rules of address in Russia: A Sociological Culture”, *Language in society*, London, 2005. – 152 p.
3. Bo‘ronov J.B. *Ingliz va o‘zbek tillari qiyosiy grammatikasi*. O‘qituvchi nashriyoti, 1973 yil. 283 b.
4. Ervin-Tripp S. On sociolinguistic rules: Alternation and co-occurrence. In *Directions on Sociolinguistics*. – New York: Runehart & Winson, 2005. – P. 52.
5. Holmes J. *An Introduction to Sociolinguistics*. – London: 2nd Edition, Longman, 2001. – 304 p.
6. Ilyish B.A. *History of English*. – Moscow: “High school”, 1968. – 420 p.
7. 32 Lechner T. *Contemporary Sociolinguistics*. - Boston: Boston Social Rules of Address in English speaking countries // www.teachingenglish.org.us/think/methodology/lesson-planning.
8. 8 Lechner T. *Contemporary Sociolinguistics*. - Boston: Boston Social Scientific Press, 2010. – 262 p.
9. 36 Paulston C. B. “Pronouns of Address in English and Russian”. – Los-Angeles: “Social Class Semantics and a Changing System”, *Language in Society*, 2002. – P. 132-139.
10. Scientific Press, 2010. – 262 p.
11. Аль-Камиди, Т.Т. *Обращение в современном русском языке: автореф. дис. канд. филол. наук / Т.Т. Аль-Камиди*. Баку, 1968. - 19 с.
12. 6/ Егорова Т. П. Семантическая функция имени // *Ономастика. Материалы к серии Народы мира и культура*. – Вып. XXV. – Ч. I. – М.: РАН, 1993. – С. 21.
13. 8 Зинин С. И. *Введение в русскую антропонию*. – Ташкент: ТашГУ, 1972. – 167 с.
14. Ярцева, В.Н. *Принципы типологического исследования родственных и неродственных языков / В.Н. Ярцева // X международный конгресс лингвистов: проблемы языкознания*. М., 1967. - С. 203